

BEHAVIORAL COMPLICATIONS OF DIAGNOSED AUTISTIC CHILDREN:
CASES OF QUETTA CITY

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Abstract

Purpose of this study is to find out the common behavioral issues among diagnosed autistic children of Quetta city. Children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) show a variety of actions including sensory and repetitive behaviors, communication challenges, self-help and social behavioral challenges in their daily lives. The research design of the present study is quantitative design. For this study sample of N = 30 autistic children include boys and girls was selected from several institutes of Quetta city. The analysis was carried out by Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS- 26). For data collection Autism behavior checklist was used created by David A. Kurg, Joel Arick, & Patricia Almond (Updated By John Hookway). The result showed that there are different common behavior issues in children which are more frequent in boys than girls living with autism. The finding shows the strong need to provide customized environment and early interventions to reduce the effect of behavioral issues in autism children.

INTRODUCTION

Any action a person takes in reaction to both internal or external conditions are defined as Behavior (Campbell et al., 2015). The way people engage with their environment—such as social or environmental events—is reflected in how they behave (Uher, 2016).

Adaptive behavior patterns are a measure of mental health, according to behavioral theory. Learning can improve mental health by replacing negative habits with positive ones. Reinforcement modifies behavior. (B.F. Skinner, 1953) It is the action an individual takes to bring about a change, make something happen, or maintain the present situation. Behavior is a reaction to events that occur both internally, such as thoughts and feelings, and externally, such as the circumstances and other people.

There is a reason behind every action. Understanding the four functions of behavior is

necessary in order to understand the motivation behind a child's actions, promote positive behaviors, and discourage problematic behaviors. These four functions given by Brian Iwata enable us to understand an individual's behavior as well as identify the causes of behaviors.

Attention is the primary purpose of behavior. A person engages in attention-seeking actions when they want a response or feedback from another person.

Escape is goal of behavior. When a learner wants to "escape" or avoid doing something, they usually engage in escape behaviors.

It should be rather obvious that having **access to tangibles** is crucial and another purpose of behavior. When kids act in specific ways, it could be because they want to get something.

Behavior's next main objective is **sensory stimulation**, sometimes referred to as sensory demands.

When children seek to substitute discomfort with a pleasurable experience, sensory stimulation takes place. Brian Iwata (1994).

Our interactions with our physical and social surrounds are influenced by sensory processing, which enables us to arrange information from the body and the environment. Infants' activities are influenced by sensory processing from birth through reflexive motor actions and state regulation. Stein and Rowland (2011)

Environmental factors greatly influence behaviour problems in people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Modabbernia, et, all, (2017) states behaviour problems such as prenatal maternal infections, stress, and exposure to heavy metals or certain medications may have an effect on neurodevelopment and may cause behaviour problems. Perinatal difficulties, such as prematurity or birth trauma, further increase the risk of behaviour problems. Postnatal symptoms such as anxiety, aggression, and sensitivity to sensory input may be worsened by environmental contamination exposure, dietary factors, and an unbalanced microbiome gut (De Magistris et al., 2010).

The multifaceted role of environment and genetic in autism behaviour is further supported by psychosocial stressors such as trauma, irregular routines, and family stress that also contribute to behaviour abnormalities in ASD. According to the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ), children with ASD experienced more issues in every domain than children with other difficulties. In the ASD sample, SDQ scores were linked to higher levels of family socioeconomic risk, male sex, living in a home with more children, more severe autism symptoms, and fewer adaptive abilities. Hastings et al. (2021) few studies have been conducted on the behavioral and emotional issues that children with ASD face in special education settings. Only a small percentage of children with ASD and intellectual disabilities sought mental health services, according to a UK study that found high levels of emotional and behavioral problems (Salomone et al. 2014).

In contrast to a group with multiple disabilities, teachers of students in a Singaporean primary special

school population reported that students with ASD had higher levels of behavioral issues, such as disruptive/harmful behavior, self-absorption, speech disturbance, anxiety, and social relating (Poon 2012). In Singapore, parents of children aged 6-18 with ASD who attend special schools reported high levels of worry across the ability spectrum (Magiati et al., 2016).

Another study results offer evidence for at least two underlying causes of these behaviors (food reactions and insensitivity to pain), along with treatment implications. Even more than that, a number of behaviors that are frequently seen in early childhood may be early indicators of these problematic behaviors Edelson (2021)

A Japanese survey carried out in 2017 by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology to gather data for teacher assistance on behavioral issues in students revealed 63,325 cases of violence. There were 28,315 occurrences in elementary schools, 28,702 in middle schools, and 6308 in high schools; 4.8 cases per 1000 students were reported. These incidents included property damage, interactions between students and teachers, and incidents involving other people.

According to research, the frequency and severity of aggressive behavior in people with ASD may be significantly decreased by therapeutic approaches such as functional behavioral evaluation, reinforcement techniques, and functional communication training. The creation of efficient therapeutic and pharmacologic strategies for preventing and managing aggressiveness is crucial to improving outcomes in ASD, given the steadily rising diagnosis rate. Fitzpatrick et al. (2016).

This group of disorders, which are brought on by abnormalities in the development of the brain, includes a delayed social and language skill development, difficulty switching between activities, repetitive behaviors, difficulty focusing on specific details, unusual emotional reactions, and an inability to understand social signals or rules. WHO 2022 Current study is focused on common behavioral issues in children with autism in Quetta city where parents face a lot of challenging behaviour in their kids diagnosed with autism that affects parent's mental health and self-efficacy. The purpose of the

study is to highlight problematic behavioral issues in autism children

Behavioral problems

Among children with autism, those with more severe symptoms and impairments tend to have more behavioral problems Fodstad et al. (2012). Anger (against oneself, one's classmates, or one's caretakers), Self-harming actions (such as biting, scratching, and head-banging), Lack of emotional regulation and tantrums, Impulsivity and hyperactivity, Repetitive and specific behaviors include hand flapping, rocking, and matching objects. Transitional difficulties and rigidity (aversion to routine changes), Avoidance and social disengagement, issues with sensory processing (over- or under-responsiveness to sensory input), Sleep issues and inconsistent routines, eating problems (food choice, limited diet). Furthermore, autism frequently co-occurs with behavioral issues such as aggression, tantrums, inattention/hyperactivity, anxiety, sensory issues, phobias, and trouble sleeping (Goldin, Matson, & Cervantes, 2014).

Research suggests that rates of aggressive behavior may be higher in people with autism than in peers who are usually developing, and those who have other developmental disorders. Aggression is more common in people with comorbid autism and intellectual disability than in people with ID alone, according to Fitzpatrick et al. (2016).

On the other hand, one study found that younger autism children exhibited less aggression than an age-matched control group, despite the fact that older autism children in study showed higher rates of anger Farmer et al. (2015).

One of the primary characteristics of autism spectrum disorders is restricted and repetitive behaviors. Leekam, prior, and Uljarevic (2011). Children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) mainly show restrictive repetitive behaviors and struggles with social skills, communication, and interaction.

Experts think these could be due to a complicated relationship between neurological, genetic, and cognitive factors (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Langen et al. (2011) stated that neuroimaging studies pointed out the abnormalities in their prefrontal

cortex and basal ganglia, which are related to the emergence of repetitive behaviors and problems with social cognition. Also, genetic factors like alterations and genetic polymorphisms that affect synaptic activity have been associated with language development delays and abnormal social behaviors (Abrahams & Geschwind, 2008).

Present study highlights different behavioral issues that were linked with autism children.

These behavior issues have impacts on children life in dealing with daily life challenges

Methods

Research Design

The quantitative research approach is used because it enables the researcher to obtain facts rather than make inferences about the study's goal. It is an efficient method that ability to test hypotheses, and a constant focus on explaining characteristics quantifying them, and developing statistical models to account for what is noticed while conducting research **Objective**

- To examine the common behavioral issues among autistic children.

Sample

The study comprised with thirty (30) diagnosed Autism children with 23 boys and 7 girls, with an average age of 6.5 years. Purposive sampling techniques was used to collect data.

Research Tool

- a) Inform consent
- b) Demographic information Form
- c) Autism Behaviour Checklist (ABC)

This Autism Behaviour Checklist (ABC), created by David A. Kurg, Joel Arick, and Patricia Almond Updated by John Hookway (3 Aug -2024), to evaluate behavioral traits associated with autism spectrum disorder. The checklist, consisting of 66 structured items, screened for observable behaviour in children with autism, ensuring the validity of the findings. The ABC Checklist completed by child parents.

Statistical Analysis

For the purpose of statistical analysis, the most recent 26th version of the "Statistical Package for

Social Sciences" used to statistically measure the behavioral problems of autistic children. The technique of Analysis was using descriptive statistics.

Results

As the study focus on common behavior issues of autism in four domains Sensory behaviors, relating behaviors, body and object use behaviors, language behaviors, social and self- help skills result reflects that child faces many common behavioral issues.

Table 1

Domains	Behaviors
Sensory Behaviors	Bright light sensitivities, loud voice sensitivity, poor visual discrimination
Relating Behaviors	Weak socialization skills, difficulty making friends, weak eye contact; poor imitation; difficulty waiting turns
Body and Object Use Behaviors	Hand flapping, toe walking, repetitive behaviors (stimming), inappropriate use of objects
Language Behaviors	Unaware of surroundings, echolalia (repetition of sentences), object obsession
Social and Self-Help Skills	Engages in self-injurious behavior, weak self-help skills, difficulty adapting to change

Table 1 indicates the common behaviors in different domains of autism behavior

Table 2

Table of Frequency distribution based on gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Boys	23	76.7
Girls	7	23.3
Total	30	100.0

Note: (N= 30)

Table 2 shows the Frequency distribution based on gender groups where the percentage of boys are 76.7% and girls are 23.3%.

Table 3

Score distribution of children age in average years

Statistic	Value
Mean	6.56
Standard Deviation	2.75
Range	11.00
Minimum	3.00
Maximum	14.00

Note. N = 30

Table 3 show the Score distribution of children age in average years. (N_30). Having Mean, Standard deviation, Minimum and Maximum Range

Discussion

Autism spectrum disorder is a condition that slows children’s development, result problems in social life. This study focuses on behavioral issues in children with autism, and data was collected from various institutions in Quetta.

In the present study, result shows that behavioral issues are more common in boys than girls with average age of 6.5 years. These problems can include difficulty in self-advocacy, forming relationships or expressing needs.

Environmental Factors are vital. Although there may be a genetic tendency toward autism, a nurturing environment can result in more favorable outcomes for the child. Given the considerable influence of behavior problems on the social development, learning, and relationships of children with autism, they have been extensively studied. Studies show that children with autism spectrum disorder tend to demonstrate a variety of behavioral problems including aggressive, violent, hyperactive, self-harming, and repetitive restrictive type behaviors (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

These behaviors not only exacerbate the child’s difficulties with peer relationships and academic achievement but also create significant stress for the parents and other caregivers (Fitzpatrick et al., 2016). Most of these behaviors arise from problems with interacting and handling feelings. When children struggle to express their needs, desires, or difficulties, challenging behaviors may emerge as an alternative way to engage. (Leekam, Prior, & Uljarevic, 2011).

Being a sensitive to certain things, like sounds or textures, pushes these reactions and can make them

avoid or get upset in hard moments. Even though these behaviors can be difficult to deal with, it’s important to see that they often have a use, like calm themselves, getting attention, or running away from things they don’t want to do (Iwata et al., 1994).

This way of thinking points out that it’s important to find ways to handle the behavior that fix the problems and just stop them. Strategy like ABA, social building, and family help have shown to do a good job in making the worse behaviors better and helping them deal (Matson et al., 2009).

Amongst Children with autism often experience unmet needs, communication difficulties, sensory processing difficulties, and learning delays. A holistic and adapted approach that involves parents, teachers, and therapists should be taken to reduce challenging behaviors and to promote positive developmental outcomes.

This study focuses on several behaviors in children with autism, including sensory behaviors, interpersonal behaviors, object use, language and communication, self-care abilities, and social skills.

Conclusion

To sum up, anger and self-harming actions are common behaviors in children with autism. Tantrums and lack of emotional regulation, impulsivity and hyperactivity, Repetitive and specific behaviors are hand flapping, rocking, and making sequences of objects. Include rigidity and difficulty adjusting to change, Avoidance and social disengagement, problems with sensory processing, irregular sleep patterns, irregular schedules, and

difficulties with eating such restricted choices for food.

However, these behaviors are not always harmful but are also the child's way to communicate, and express what they want in any way. Finding underlying causes and problems can help us to prevent the increasing rate of autistic behaviors in children. Early interventions and a customized environment can help the child to cope with all these behavior problems very well in life.

Limitations

Yet, there was a limitations in this research. That our society continues to stigmatize mental illness. Some parents have refused to provide information and they hesitate to report behavior or openly discuss concerns to their children. Understanding the prevalence of common behavioral concerns among children with autism spectrum disorder is limited due to the forms, severity, and setting of such behaviors are themselves highly variable, so it is challenging to generalize the results from different studies to the entire population of children with ASD.

The majority of literature on behavioral concerns among children with ASD relies on their parent or teacher reports of such behaviors, some of these observations may be subjective and minor acts may have been missed.

Moreover, there may be cultural differences in defining or interpreting such behaviors, differences in the diagnostic criteria used, or limitations in the resources available. More longitudinal and cross-cultural studies are thus needed to better raise the value of the complexities of behavioral concerns among children with ASD and to develop more inclusive and generalizable approaches.

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